

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

Assessment Framework Report

Framework for the Mapping and Analysis of Agroecology and Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in Europe

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Deliverable Number	D2.1
Work Package	2
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable leader	Aarhus University, Department of Agroecology
Due date	31 March 2021
Submission date	April 2022
Version	Final
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History of changes

Revision	Date	Authors	Comments
First internal draft	14 January 2022	Torsten Rødel Berg, Martin Thorsoe Hvarregaard	Draft circulated for comments from AU WP2 team
Second external draft	01 March 2022	Torsten Rødel Berg, Martin Thorsoe Hvarregaard	Draft circulated for comments from All- Ready/WP2 partners
Final report	22 March 2022	Torsten Rødel Berg	All comments incorporated

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Table of Contents

Introduction	4
1. ARRIVING AT THE FRAMEWORK	5
1.1 DYNAMIC EXTERNAL CONDITIONS	5
1.1.1 Division of work and collaboration between the CSAs	5
1.2. STRUCTURE AND SCOPE OF THE ALL-READY MAPPING TASK	5
1.2.1 Collaboration with AE4EU	5
1.2.2. The WP1 'conditions and criteria' inputs	6
2. THE MAPPING FRAMEWORK	7
2.1 MIX OF METHODS	7
2.1.1 Identifying National Contact Points.....	8
2.1.2 Preparation for and conducting interviews for the mapping	8
2.1.3 The phase 2 survey	9
2.1.4 Key concepts and definitions	10
2.1.5 Data management and analysis.....	11
3. CONCLUDING REMARKS	11
ANNEX 1 - INTERVIEW SUPPORTING DOCUMENTS	13
1. INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	13
2. REPORTING TEMPLATE.....	23
2.1 SECTION OVERVIEW	23
2.2 TEMPLATE FOR THE REPORTING OF CLOSED QUESTIONS.....	24
ANNEX 2 - INFORMATION LETTER FOR COLLECTING RESEARCH DATA	28
ANNEX 3 - COUNTRIES TO BE MAPPED	30

List of abbreviations

AELL	Agroecology Living Labs
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
FACCE-JPI	Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food security and Climate change
LL	Living Lab
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
R&I	Research and Innovation
SCAR AE SWG	Standing Committee on Agriculture Strategic Working Group on Agroecology and Living Labs
WP	Work Package

Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This report explains the approach and methodologies (the mapping framework from now on) employed in the mapping and analysis tasks conducted under Work Package (WP) 2 "Mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms for carrying out participatory agroecological research and innovation including KPI's for the network". Specifically, this is a framework for the mapping and analysis of agroecology initiatives, agroecology LLs and agroecology RIs in twenty-three countries in Europe (Turkey, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Slovakia, Serbia, Poland, Norway, Lichtenstein, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Latvia, Ireland, Iceland, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Czech Republic, Cyprus, Belgium, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Hungary). The latter 5 countries are mapped jointly with the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) AE4EU¹.

The report contributes to the ALL-Ready and the wider Partnership on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures objectives. In line with the task description in the ALL-Ready project proposal (the project document from now on), the report offers a framework for the mapping and analysis of existing agroecology initiatives, RIs, LLs and other open innovation arrangements (OIA) known to strengthen the transition to agroecology, along with their underpinning funding sources and regulatory contexts. Within this scope, the framework is designed to identify drivers, barriers and incentives to agroecology transition, with particular attention to agroecology LLs and RIs, agroecology practices as well as policies and regulatory aspects.

The framework has benefited from the characterisations and definitions of what constitutes agroecological production, agri-food systems and agroecological LLs and RIs, prepared in WP1², as well as key agroecology literature. The guidelines prepared by the CSA AE4EU for a comparable mapping exercise have also served as inspiration, not least in terms of identifying supplementing information needs.

The mapping framework serves specifically to generate information for the following deliverables (D): D2.3 Report on drivers of agroecology transition; D2.4 Overview of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures in Europe; D2.5 Agroecology open Innovation: best cases across Europe; D2.6 Towards a network of agroecology living labs.

¹ A total of 39 countries are mapped by the CSAs ALL-Ready and AE4EU

² Deliverables D1.1 'Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition' and D1.2 'Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies'

1. Arriving at the Framework

1.1 Dynamic external conditions

While the ALL-Ready WP2 mapping exercise is described in the ALL-Ready project document in some detail, unforeseen elements of complexity with respect to the mapping approach arose even before the beginning of ALL-Ready.

These complexities stem primarily from efforts to enhance collaboration with the AE4EU CSA's parallel mapping exercise and the need to align ALL-Ready deliverable schedules with that of the Standing Committee on Agriculture Strategic Working Group on Agroecology and Living Labs (SCAR AE SWG), under the auspices of which the AE Partnership is being developed.

1.1.1 Division of work and collaboration between the CSAs

Acknowledging the benefits of coordination and avoiding duplication of work, the first steps towards aligning the ALL-Ready and AE4EU mapping exercise entailed exploration, of the possibility of conducting a joint mapping exercise. However, it was decided to design and carry out two separate, yet complementary, exercises. This was due to conceptual and methodological differences between the two CSAs, as reflected in the respective project documents which constitute the terms of reference for the mapping tasks. The task descriptions of these documents differ in terms of methodological approach, which again, to a considerable extent, reflect the respective expertise and co-creation endeavors in the two consortia.

This has led to a division of work, whereby the 39 countries are divided between the two CSAs, reflecting respective strengths in relation to specific countries, such as the presence of AE4EU or ALL-Ready stakeholders and existing knowledge about agroecology, living lab and research infrastructure landscapes. This has also resulted in five countries being mapped jointly (see annex 3 for the list of countries).

Despite the division of work, the two CSAs constantly seek to enhance the value of the mapping to the European Commission and the Partnership, to the CSAs academically and as networks, by data sharing, and by continuously seeking to identify areas where thematic collaboration is mutually meaningful and beneficial.

1.2. Structure and scope of the ALL-Ready mapping task

1.2.1 Collaboration with AE4EU

The scoping and mapping framework development process has benefited from All-Ready and AE4EU collaboration early in the project period. The CSAs share a basic conceptual basis, which reflects the useful and dominant scoping of agroecology as a scientific discipline, a set of practices, and a social and political movement (see Wezel et al. 2009). However, a series of meetings, internally in ALL-Ready and with AE4EU, elucidated conceptual and methodological differences between the two CSAs, and as an outcome of the process, helped define the scope and structuring of the ALL-Ready mapping task.

While All-Ready also pays attention to aspects such as solidarity economy and values of social justice, its overall approach focuses on the *science* and *practice* pillars of agroecology, and compared to AE4EU, less on agroecology as a *movement*. Policy drivers also receive considerable attention in All-Ready. Additionally, ALL-Ready has a relatively strong focus on the mapping of institutional mechanisms for fostering innovation in agroecology transition, e.g agroecology LLs and related RIs and OIAs.

The AE4EU approach to mapping considers agroecology RIs as part of the *science* pillar, and perceives LLs as associated with the *practice* pillar. Conceptually, this framework diverges from ALL-Ready, where the institutional arrangements – particularly the LLs - in support of AE transition cut across the *practice* and *science* pillars as co-creation spaces where farming practice at the level of primary production meets research endeavors to develop joint solutions, with agroecology supportive RIs often coming into the picture as well. The policy dimension also cuts across and adds the mapping of key structural drivers and barriers to both the *practice* and the *science* pillars of agroecology.

In sum, ALL-Ready structures the investigation around *practice* and *science* with LLs and RIs as transversal and integrating themes and with *policy* as a structural determinant. This structure and scope has had bearings on the overall design of the investigation, including the nature of respondents, themes and the data that may be collected, as described in the next section.

1.2.2. The WP1 'conditions and criteria' inputs

The boundaries of the agroecology concept are wide, blurred and contested. However, the basic scope of the mapping task reflects the ALL-Ready project document, which stipulates a focus on agroecology projects and programmes, institutional mechanisms such as LLs, OIAs, RIs and policies that affect agroecology, at the primary production level.

Based on the D1.1 work on the conditions for agroecology transition, along with the criteria and indicators for identifying organisations for possible inclusion in the future network of LLs and RIs established in D1.2, the All-Ready CSA maps the landscape in a transition context. Hence, the focus is on the initiatives, the policies and institutional arrangements across Europe that sustain transition. This is with the ambition to gain an overview of the 'landscape' and understand enablers, barriers and incentives for innovation for agroecology transition.

D1.1 identified four main conditions: appropriate values surrounding human-environment and human-human interactions; appropriate socio-economic, cultural, agro-ecosystem, and environmental activities; appropriate policy incentives; and, appropriate skills, knowledge, and competencies amongst all food chain actors. D1.1. further indicated how RIs and LLs can contribute to the agroecology transition by strengthening societal competencies in each of the four areas described above. The concepts developed in D1.1 thus represent the foundation for the ongoing project and for the other WPs that work towards a European network of RIs and LLs..

Specifically, the types of activities that can highlight a significant engagement in agroecology transition were screened and organised into two main categories: those undertaken at the agroecosystem level, and those orientating the way they are implemented, with an openness to the socio-cultural-economic context (which satisfied the four main conditions outlined in D1.1.). Under those categories, groups of activities are detailed. Being a key player for agroecology transition means undertaking at least one activity in each category as e.g. when an organisation aims to develop synergies between elements of the agroecosystem (crop and animal production).

If this is done through a co-creation process with multi-stakeholder engagement, then there is a better chance to drive and accelerate agroecology transition. Co-creation with multi-stakeholders is a demanding process, for which exchange of practice, reliance on accurate knowledge and provision of data to characterise the evolution of the system concerned, are essential. LLs and RIs are built on specific principles [for LLs: co-creation, involving users, under real-life conditions; for RIs: prototyping agroecosystem design and redesign] and are able to provide accurate orientations for capacity building of organisations willing to accelerate the transition process. These benefits can then be added to the future network.

Figure 1: Agroecology Research Infrastructure and Living Lab Criteria and Indicators

As depicted in figure 1, above, WP1 in D1.2 further developed the criteria and indicators to enable the project to identify organisations for a possible inclusion in the future network of LLs and RIs. The criteria and indicators are meant to be used for organisations that might be able to strengthen the transition to agroecology across Europe. These include organisations that are already actively involved in the agroecology transition, whose involvement in the agroecology transition could be accelerated by their belonging to the network and/or whose involvement in the network will be beneficial to other network members.

This strategy was chosen in order to enable the mapping exercise in WP2 to include organisations that function as agroecology LLs or RIs, even if they do not use such terms to describe their activities. The criteria were built with a view to focusing, delimiting and standardising the mapping, analysis and principles of agroecology transition processes in WP2.

2. The mapping framework

The WP2 mapping tasks consist of a phase 1 and a phase 2 survey. The approach of the phase 1 survey is as follows.

2.1 Mix of methods

To ensure comparability across the countries that are surveyed, the mapping exercise is based on a survey among key informants (national contact points – NCPs - see below) to provide an overview of country level implementation of regulatory frameworks, funding institutions and current national agroecology initiatives, LLs and RIs. This information constitutes indicators for estimating levels of transition, barriers and drivers, as well as inquiries into transition processes in selected national contexts.

The number of contributing participants, the great variation in country contexts to be explored, along with the wide scope of the deliverables require interview guidelines that ensure reasonably comparable data across countries and consortia. Hence, the guidelines specify the type of information needed from the different countries, enabling the acquiring of information on a national level, and the compiling of information in a national reporting format that feeds into the WP2 deliverables.

Subsequently, the interview guidelines which have been developed (see annex 1) for obtaining country-level data, apply a combination of closed and open questions. The former questions allow for direct comparison across countries, while the latter questions provide a basis for a broader qualitative analysis, and for detailed description of perspectives. This mix of methods aims to ensure a rich picture of the situation within the different countries.

Organising the data collection: Data collection is based on a progression with three phases:

1. Identification of key informants – national contact points (see below).
2. A survey among national contact points (NCP) (key informants), providing a comparable and broad overview of the situation across countries, as a basis for clarifying the national contexts and identifying local initiatives.
3. A more detailed qualitative follow up phase that focuses on the situation in selected member states and engages with stakeholders who are members of selected agroecology LLs and OIAs identified in the survey.

2.1.1 Identifying National Contact Points

The phase 1 mapping framework entails interviews with NCPs in every country, within three broad stakeholder domains: (i) policy/authorities (typically case officers in ministries), (ii) research, and (iii) civil society institutions and associations that are relevant in relation to agroecology transition. As key informants, the NCPs are expected to have in-depth knowledge about the agricultural sector in their countries, yet represent different perspectives.

Note that key informants enable the collection of information that can be used analytically, not information that that can be generalised statistically. NCPs from the policy/authority sector are identified, initially, through FACCE-JPI, a Europe-wide initiative that gathers agroecology relevant expertise. Thereafter, snowballing allows the identification of further NCPs with the aim of covering the three main stakeholder domains in the countries.

2.1.2 Preparation for and conducting interviews for the mapping

Interviewers, most of whom have research backgrounds and/or other relevant academic expertise, are sourced from the WP2 mapping team for carrying out the mapping. They each handle a portfolio of countries, allocated on the basis of the researcher's specific qualifications in relation to specific countries, including linguistic skills where needed (the NCPs do not necessarily speak English).

Based on the list of NCPs, the All-Ready researchers (interviewers) send the interview guide to the NCPs in advance. Then, the interviews are conducted virtually or by phone (or if possible, at a physical meeting). The varying professional backgrounds of the NCPs mean that not all NCPs are able to relate to all questions. The researchers assess this on a case-to-case basis and adjust accordingly. In some cases, such as when the identified NCPs do not cover all categories for a country, or when responses are deemed inadequate, the researcher may apply snowballing techniques identifying alternative respondents.

In many cases, researchers also carry out background (desktop) studies identifying relevant country-specific policies, research infrastructures etc. This is in order to become familiar with relevant national contexts, in order to make the most of the interviews.

2.1.3 The phase 2 survey

The phase 2 survey is based on an online questionnaire which operationalises the inclusion criteria described in D1.2 (see 1.2.2, above). The questionnaire simplifies the criteria to ensure comprehension by participants who are not fully familiar with the concept of agroecology transition. It is distributed amongst the agroecology-related initiatives that have been identified by NCPs during the phase 1 mapping survey.

The online tool combines open and closed questions. The closed questions enable the project to understand if a specific organisation is fulfilling the criteria for agroecology transition, and to what extent. The open questions enable the project to collect in-depth information, and to collect examples; they are screening the five main dimensions depicted in Figure 2:

Figure 2: The Five Screening Dimensions

The final questions that specifically address the organisation's budget and funding provide information useful to other deliverables (as often local and regional LLs and RIs are funded by regional or even private funders). Other questions allow the project to get an estimated overview of the LLs and RIs within many countries across Europe. The online questionnaire is initially sent to LLs and RIs in the ALL-Ready pilot network (created in WP3) to gain information about the composition of the network, but also to evaluate the ease of use of the online tool. Afterwards, the questionnaire is sent to all the organisations identified during the phase 1 mapping, through the NCPs of each country, as well as to various organisations that are linked through the European network of Living Labs (EnoLL)

The outcomes of the online questionnaire can be used for several deliverables of WP2. This includes D2.2, which investigates the funding initiatives for agroecology-relevant initiatives across Europe. The questionnaire will produce information about regional and local funding schemes of LLs and RIs, which is hard to find through desk-based research. Similarly, we expect to collect information for D2.4, which aims to give an overview of LLs and RIs across Europe.

Additionally, the questionnaire will gather data for D2.5, which reviews 'best cases' of agroecology in Europe. Here, the questionnaire makes it possible to situate responding

organisations within the transition process, and identify 'best case' examples. The organisations thus identified through the questionnaire can be further followed up with to produce fully fleshed out profiles, and in further analytical steps, e.g. for the analysis of the value added of a European Network in WP4. In addition, the questionnaire will gather data relevant to WP4 such as information on funding sources. Finally, the online questionnaire can be adapted from a tool for collecting data about organisations, to one which collects data about networks. This, and the possible relevance for other deliverables of other WPs, will be further discussed.

2.1.4 Key concepts and definitions

The interview guide contains concepts – sometimes ambiguous - that need to be well understood by both the researcher and the respondents. Guidance for the researchers serves to ensure that they are able to explain the following key concepts to the respondents:

Agroecology Transition is usually thought of as entailing different stages (Hill 2014, Gliessman 2016, WP1, D1): *Efficiency*, which connotes better use of resources within existing farming modes; *substitution*, which connotes the replacement of technologies, and; *redesign* of the agroecosystem so that it functions on the basis of ecological processes. Contrary to the additive and incremental nature of efficiency and substitution measures, redesign addresses farming systems in a more transformative fashion and maximises the coproduction of agricultural and environmental outcomes. The further along the efficiency-substitution-redesign gradient we climb, the higher the need for local agricultural knowledge and adaptation of known practices and in turn, cooperation and knowledge exchange (Pretty et al 2018).

Living labs are defined by the European Network of Living labs (ENoLL) as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation (R&I) processes in real life communities and settings”.

The definition of **agroecology living labs** is based on that of **agroecosystem living labs**, which have been defined in the draft proposal for an agroecology partnership³ as:

“transdisciplinary approaches which involve farmers, scientists and other interested partners in the co-design, monitoring and evaluation of new and existing agricultural practices and technologies on working landscapes to improve their effectiveness and early adoption”. The changing of practices through co-creation and participative processes is considered conducive to the acceleration of agroecology transition’ (see WP1, D1.1).

Research infrastructures are defined broadly as facilities that provide resources and services to conduct research and foster innovation. They include: major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; collections, archives or scientific data; computing systems and communication networks; any other R&I infrastructure of a unique nature which is open to external users.

In an agroecology transition perspective, the scope of these research infrastructures could include agriculture and agri-food redesign, sustainability assessment (impacts, ecosystem services, ecological, social and economic dimensions), vulnerability - adaptability - resilience assessment (emergent properties of agroecosystems) and dynamics of agroecology transition.

Also, from a transition perspective, RIs should have defined science-society-policy-user interfaces. When providing central roles to users –such as farmers – these infrastructures may become open innovation arrangements that resemble living labs (see WP1, D1.1)

³ The candidate Horizon Europe partnership: [“Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures”](#)

Agroecological principles and elements: see <https://www.agroecology-europe.org/our-approach/principles/> as well as <http://www.fao.org/3/i9037en/i9037en.pdf>.

Agroecological practices: In agriculture, see <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7>

Stakeholders are typically farmers, farmer groups or associations that develop and implement agroecological practices. This includes Community Supported Agriculture schemes and local product distribution channels, as well as other stakeholder initiatives that have a clear orientation towards agroecology. Further stakeholders potentially involved in agroecological initiatives are value chain actors, consumers, citizens and policy-makers.

2.1.5 Data management and analysis

The Phase 1 and Phase 2 surveys generate data for the following deliverables:

D2.3 Report on drivers of agroecology transition

D2.4 Overview of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures in Europe

D2.5 Agroecology open Innovation: best cases across Europe

D2.6 Towards a network of agroecology living labs

Having completed the results of interviews with the NCPs, the interviewers compile results into a brief country report, summarising the key findings of the interviews in a template (see interview guidelines, annex 1). Interviewers also write a narrative summary of key issues that emerge from the interviews. Interviewers will also report and reflect on divergences across the informants, internal variation within the countries and on the methodology applied.

As a next step, a WP2 analysis team screens reports and compiles data in a spreadsheet, which is subsequently shared with deliverable leads for use in the preparation of the individual reports. The WP2 mapping team is cognizant of the interdependence and complementarities between deliverables, as well as the value of deliverables as regards informing work in other WPs, and WP leads coordinate these matters regularly.

3. Concluding remarks

This report has explained the framework for WP2 mapping and analysis tasks. The scope and structure of the mapping has evolved in a dynamic context, in which the stipulations of the project document (reflecting the skills, the thinking and the structure of the ALL-Ready consortium), the AE Partnership formulation process, and the AE4EU approach have been taken into consideration.

The outcome is a framework where the mapping is structured around LLs and RIs as transversal and integrating themes, with policy drivers seen as a determinant in agroecology transition, investigated by means of a qualitative investigation centered on key informants.

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- All-Ready Work Package 1, Deliverable D1.1: Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition' and D1.2 'Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies.
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Annex 1 - Interview supporting documents

1. Interview guide

The interview guide contains (1) closed questions as well as (2) a series of in-depth open-ended questions that allow for broadening the response to the closed questions and provide additional reflections.

The varying professional backgrounds (typically administration, research or civil society) of the NCPs mean that not all NCPs may be able to respond to all questions. The interviewer will need to assess this on a case to case basis. Following the interviews, the interviewer will complete a synthesis of the interviews, including the sources of information. Find the template for this in the next section.

Please complete one template for each NCP and before each interview please ensure that participants consent to the conditions of data collection as described in the “Information letter for collecting research data” found in appendix 1 of this guideline document.

Before commencing the interview, please explain the objective of the project, as outlined in section one, (introduction). Refer also to section 2, for explaining key concepts and definitions. Do not assume that the respondent knows these concepts.

• Background information

1. For the interviewer: Please record the following background information of the interview:

- a) Country : _____
- b) NPC interviewed (name) _____
- c) Organisation: _____

2. Which of the following stakeholder categories do you belong to?

Public administration (e.g. government, municipality, funding body etc.)	
Researcher/Scientist	
NGO (e.g. farmers associations or other association, think-tank, etc.) (please specify) _____	

• Defining Agroecology

Agroecology is a broad and complex concept. It is generally seen as a scientific field, a practice and a social movement. It is common to find different understandings and emphases within these three areas. This section explores these differences.

3. On a scale from 1-5 how important are the different dimensions of agroecology in your country?

	(1) Very important	(2) Important	(3) Neutral	(4) Less important	(5) Unimportant	(x) I don't know
Practices – E.g. production practices that reduce input us, save resources, are characterised by diversity; agricultural systems and food systems where stakeholders (incl. farmers, consumers, authorities) are involved in decision-making, co-creating innovation etc.						
Science – E.g. research on applying ecological concepts and principles to optimise interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment (agronomy + ecology), in agricultural systems and food systems)						
Social Movements – E.g. NGOs, cooperatives etc with focus on small-scale, family farming, food sovereignty, promoting values (incl. solidarity, rights, ecological justice) indigenous (diverse) seeds/breeds etc						

4. Other reflections regarding the understanding of agroecology in your country?

• The extent of agroecology-based practices within the country

5. On a scale from 1 to 5 how commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?

	(1) Very common	(2) Common	(3) Neutral	(4) Somewhat	(5) Unusual	(x) I don't know
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling						
Biodiversity Preservation						

Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration with Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Other						

6. If other, please describe principles and/or practices and clarify extent of application:

7. Are there regional differences with respect to the extent of application? Where and why is this the case?

8. Other reflections regarding the extent of agroecology related principles and/or practices in your country?

• **Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology**

Agroecology is considered as a key element in the green transition envisaged in key strategy documents, such as the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy etc.

9. On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in your country?

	(1) To a high	(2) To some	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited	(5) Not at all	(x) I don't know
Research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transition						
Research programs have focus on agroecological transition						
Sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices						

Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are sufficiently reflected in current research activities						
Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation						
On farm experimentation is often applied in research activities						

10. How can current research infrastructures **be used** to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices?

11. How can current research infrastructures and research programmes **be improved** to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices?

12. Other reflections regarding research infrastructures in your country?

• **Competencies for an agroecological transition**

13. On a scale from 1 to five, how would you classify the state of the following elements in the context of agroecology in your country?

	(1) Very well	(2) Developed	(3) Neutral	(4) Somewhat	(5) Not developed at	(x) I don't know
Education of farmers in agricultural colleges						
Technological infrastructure in the farming sector						
Knowledge networks among farmers						
Farm advisory service						

Resources available for training/retraining of farmers						
Farmer networks for knowledge sharing						
Other						

14. If other, please specify:

15. Other reflections regarding competencies for an agroecological transition?

• **Involvement of stakeholders in the agroecological transition**

16. On a scale from 1 to (4) five to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in your country?

	(1) To a high extent	(2) To some extent	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited	(5) not at all	(X) I don't know
Stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests						
Stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise						
Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking						
Stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes						
Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition						
Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used in to foster transition within your country						
Stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs						

17. How can the involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transition be improved in the

17

country (in living labs and other open innovation arrangements)?

18. Which stakeholder groups are primarily involved in the agroecological transition and are any stakeholder groups lacking?

19. Other reflections regarding the involvement of stakeholder in the agroecological transition

• **Policies in Support of Agroecological transition**

20. On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecological transition?

	(1) To a high extent	(2) To some extent	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited	(5) Not at all	(x) I don't know
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration/Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs						
Other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (eg communities of practice, farmer field schools etc)						

21. If other, please specify

22. Which specific policies are the most relevant for the transition towards agroecology in your country - and why?

23. What are the most important limitations in national and European policies with respect to agroecology in your country?

24. Other reflections regarding policies supporting an agroecological transition?

• **Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices**

25. On a scale from 1 to 5, to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures?

	(1) Fully agree	(2) Agree	(3) Neutral	(4) Partly agree	(5) Disagree	(x) I don't know
Current <u>national</u> policies sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
Current <u>European</u> policies sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
Resource allocations are sufficient to support agroecological transition						
Advisory systems sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
A transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in my country						

The current organization of the food market supports agroecological initiatives						
The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system sufficiently foster an agroecological transition						

26. What are the most important barriers for an agroecological transition in the country, and why are these barriers seen as important?

27. Other reflections regarding opportunities for advancing agroecology-based production methods?

• **Best practice examples of agroecology initiatives**

For the forthcoming partnership we need to showcase best practice cases of agroecology living labs and research infrastructure in Europe. Therefore, we kindly ask you to provide information about relevant initiatives within your country. We will use this list as an entry point for further inquiry with the enlisted contact person, therefore, please provide updated contact data.

Please bear in mind that we need as many initiatives as possible, therefore, please provide an overview of as many initiatives as possible. If you need more entries, please copy/paste the table below.

Agroecology initiative #1

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	
Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (Farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	

Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

Agroecology initiative #2

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	
Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	
Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

Agroecology initiative #3

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	
Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (Farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	

Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

(Please copy/paste more if needed)

- **Ending**

28. Other messages or reflections of relevance for the themes of the survey and for the future partnership on agroecology?

2. Reporting template

When you have completed the round of interviews with the NCPs, please provide a short national report summarising the key findings of the interviews in the format given below. For each chapter, please write a small section (circa 500 words) summarising points raised in the interviews. In your text please consider and report when there are divergence across the informants as well as internal variation within the countries.

Additionally, please report all data from the closed questions in the template at the end of the list.

Please bear in mind that these sections will appear as appendices to the deliverables, therefore, please note that the text will be published fully or in parts. The report will be used to complete several deliverables, thus please avoid cross references to other chapters in the national report as they may be used in separate deliverables.

2.1 Section overview

1) Background information of the National Contact Points

- Here briefly clarify which participants were used as informants in the interviews?

2) Definitions of agroecology

- Here please elaborate how agroecology is interpreted and implemented in the country and whether there are different understandings of agroecology in use across the country.

3) The extent of agroecology-based practices

- Here please elaborate on the use of agro-ecology based practices in the country, which practices and principles are most common, which are less used and

4) Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology

- Here please elaborate on state of the research and innovation system in the country with respect to agroecology, including challenges and need for improvement.

5) Competencies for an agroecology transition

- Here please elaborate on the competencies available within the country with respect to agroecology.

6) Involvement of stakeholders in the agroecology transition

- Here please elaborate on stakeholders structure and organization within the country, including their alignment with agroecology.

7) Policies in support of agroecology

- Here please elaborate how agroecology is reflected in existing policies and which policies are most relevant with respect to agroecology transition.

8) Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices

- Here please elaborate stakeholder's reflections regarding the opportunities for advancing an agroecology transition within the country.

9) Best practice examples of agroecology living labs

23

- Please copy/paste all the table entries you have completed during your interviews with national contact points providing a full list of different and relevant initiatives in the country. Please bear in mind that it is important for the forthcoming partnership that we identify as many relevant initiatives as possible.

10) Additional reflections

- Open entry that allows you to present relevant aspects that have appeared during your inquiry or additional points raised by interviewees.

2.2 Template for the reporting of closed questions

The template should be attached the national report as appendix. Here, please note the value of the assessment provided by the interviewee (1-5) and note “x” for “I don’t know”.

	Interviewee #1	Interviewee #2	Interviewee #3	Interviewee #4	Interviewee #5	Please insert more rows if needed
Question #2 (Which of the following stakeholder categories do you belong to?) (note with “x”)						
Public administration						
Researcher/Scientist						
NGO (please specify)						
Question #3 (On a scale from 1-5 how important are the different dimensions of agroecology in your country?)						
Practices						
Science						
Social Movements						
Question #5 (On a scale from 1 to 5 how commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?)						
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						

Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration with Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Other						
Question #9 (On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in your country?)						
Research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transition						
Research programs have focus on agroecological transition						
Sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices						
Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are sufficiently reflected in current research activities						
Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation						
On farm experimentation is often applied in research activities						
Question #13 (On a scale from 1 to five, how would you classify the state of the following elements in the context of agroecology in your country?)						
Education of farmers in agricultural colleges						
Technological infrastructure in the farming sector						
Knowledge networks among farmers						
Farm advisory service						
Resources available for training/retraining of farmers						
Farmer networks for knowledge sharing						
Other						

Question #16 (On a scale from 1 to (4) five to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in your country?)						
Stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests						
Stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise						
Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking						
Stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes						
Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition						
Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used in to foster transition within your country						
Stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs						
Question #20 (On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecological transition?)						
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration/Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs						

Other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (eg communities of practice, farmer field schools etc)						
Question #25 (On a scale from 1 to 5, to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures?)						
Current <u>national</u> policies sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
Current <u>European</u> policies sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
Resource allocations are sufficient to support agroecological transition						
Advisory systems sufficiently foster agroecological transition						
A transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in my country						
The current organization of the food market supports agroecological initiatives						
The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system sufficiently foster an agroecological transition						

Annex 2 - Information letter for collecting research data

Information letter Collection of data for research

Name and organisation of data collector: (to be filled in by research team)

Name of the research participant: _____

I, _____ (the research participant), have been informed that:

1. Data is being collected as part of the project ALL-Ready.
2. Data will be used for scientific analysis, publication and dissemination activities.
3. Data will be anonymized for publication/dissemination purposes.
4. Data will be analysed by members of the ALL-Ready project.
5. Participation is voluntary.
6. Consent for participation in the project can be withdrawn at any time by contacting the data collector.

Signature: _____ (participant)

Signature: _____ (data collector)

Date _____

Article 13 - EU GDPR: "Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject"

1. Where personal data relating to a data subject are collected from the data subject, the controller shall, at the time when personal data are obtained, provide the data subject with all of the following information:

- (a) the identity and the contact details of the controller and, where applicable, of the controller's representative;
- (b) the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable; *Please contact Aarhus University at dpo@au.dk*
- (c) the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing;
- (d) where the processing is based on point (f) of [Article 6\(1\)](#), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party;
- (e) the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any;
- (f) where applicable, the fact that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a third country or international organization and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in [Article 46](#) or [47](#), or the second subparagraph of [Article 49\(1\)](#), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means by which to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available.

2. In addition to the information referred to in paragraph 1, the controller shall, at the time when personal data are obtained, provide the data subject with the following further information necessary to ensure fair and transparent processing:

- (a) the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period;
- (b) the existence of the right to request from the controller access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing concerning the data subject or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability;
- (c) where the processing is based on point (a) of [Article 6\(1\)](#) or point (a) of [Article 9\(2\)](#), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;
- (d) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;
- (e) whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data and of the possible consequences of failure to provide such data;
- (f) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in [Article 22\(1\)](#) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.

3. Where the controller intends to further process the personal data for a purpose other than that for which the personal data were collected, the controller shall provide the data subject prior to that further processing with information on that other purpose and with any relevant further information as referred to in paragraph 2.

4. Paragraphs 1, 2 and 3 shall not apply where and insofar as the data subject already has the information.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant agreement ID: 101000349

Annex 3 - Countries to be mapped

Country	ALL-Ready	AE4EU
Albania		AE4EU has some first results.
Austria	Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results. MSc thesis to be carried out in 2021
Belgium	Partner country of ALL-Ready, Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results. Partner country of AE4EU
Bosnia-Herzegovina		X
Bulgaria		AE4EU as having partners in Romania and Greece
Croatia		AE4EU has some first results. One stakeholder is associated partner of AE4EU
Cyprus	Member FACCE-JPI	
Czech Republic	Member FACCE-JPI	
Denmark	Partner country of ALL-Ready; Member FACCE-JPI	
Estonia	Member FACCE-JPI	
Finland	Member FACCE-JPI	
France	Partner country of ALL-Ready; Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results. Partner country of AE4EU
Germany	Partner country of ALL-Ready; Member FACCE-JPI	Partner country of AE4EU; MSc thesis to be carried out in 2021
Greece		Partner country of AE4EU
Hungary	Partner country of ALL-Ready; Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has already a specific report (Feb 2021). One stakeholder is associated partner of AE4EU
Iceland	X	
Ireland	Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results
Italy	Member FACCE-JPI	Partner country of AE4EU (2 partners)
Kosovo		X
Latvia	Member FACCE-JPI	
Lithuania	Member FACCE-JPI	
Luxembourg	X	
Malta		X
Moldavia		X
Montenegro		X
North-Macedonia		AE4EU as having partner in Greece
Norway	Member FACCE-JPI	
Poland	Member FACCE-JPI	
Portugal		X
Romania	Member FACCE-JPI	Partner country of AE4EU
Serbia	Partner country of ALL-Ready	AE4EU has some first results

Slovakia	X	
Slovenia		X
Spain	Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results. Partner country of AE4EU
Sweden	Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU has some first results. Partner country of AE4EU
Switzerland	Member FACCE-JPI	
The Netherlands	Member FACCE-JPI	
Turkey	(Non-active Member FACCE-JPI)	
United Kingdom	Partner country of ALL- Ready, Member FACCE-JPI	AE4EU have some first results. Partner country of AE4EU